

The Need for Innovative Technologies in Higher Education Educational Institutions

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Abstract. *This article discusses and analyzes the use of learning technology in collaboration in Russian language lessons. The main idea of this technology is to create conditions for active joint learning activities of students in different learning situations. The bottom line is that the student wants to acquire knowledge himself. Collaboration just gives an excellent incentive for cognitive activity, for communication, since in this case you can always count on help from comrades.*

Keywords: *learning, cooperation, joint activities, learning situations, communication, student, cognitive technology.*

The modern information society places high demands on students in terms of mastering educational material, as a result of which student overload increases sharply and learning motivation decreases.

This problem in the technology of multi-level teaching is solved by introducing the so-called basic level: some students are given a smaller volume of material, while others are given a larger volume, and due to the fact that, offering students the same volume, the teacher orients them to different levels of requirements for its mastery.

At the same time, it is mandatory for all students to master the general basic level of training.

The concept of “innovation” from Latin means renewal and improvement. In pedagogy, innovation is “the purposeful, systematic and consistent introduction into practice of original, innovative methods, methods of pedagogical actions and means, covering the entire educational process from determining its goal to the expected results” [1,24].

A number of authors, including V. Kukushkina, believe that any pedagogical technology must meet some basic methodological requirements (manufacturability criteria) [2,62].

- **conceptuality:** the need for not only scientific, didactic justification, but also psychological, philosophical and social justification. Only this approach will make it possible to reveal to students the close relationship and interpenetration of medical sciences and techniques, and will create the prerequisites for a comprehensive perception of medicine as a whole, improving the assimilation of educational material;
- **systematic:** an innovative conceptual technology must have all the signs of a system – the logic of processes, the interconnection of all its components, overall integrity;
- **efficiency:** training technology must provide a high standard of training specialists in the conditions of modern technologies and scientific achievements, also be economically feasible in terms of costs for introducing innovative teaching methods and, of course, comply with the time frame of the training program;
- **management:** involves the possibility of planning, designing educational processes, using various tools for analyzing the effectiveness of the educational process at its various stages in order to adjust it;

- visualization: the ability to use video and audio materials, designing various teaching materials, using original teaching aids and devices.

Any concept must correspond to its essence. For example, the word “technology” is of Greek origin and consists of two words – skill and art. Thus, any technology can be interpreted as conscious art and refined craftsmanship. Moreover, pedagogical technologies that work with the student’s consciousness. The errors of these technologies are not immediately visible, but clearly appear over time. Therefore, it is on pedagogical technologies and those who implement them in practice that a huge responsibility lies for the development of the education system and advanced training of students.

Classical and innovative approaches to education have always existed, competing with each other. The traditional education system has the following disadvantages: authoritarianism, the dominance of explanatory and illustrative teaching and, as a consequence, the lack of direct dialogue between teachers and students

The technology of teaching in collaboration in Russian language lessons belongs to the technologies of the humanistic direction in the methodology. The main idea of this technology is to create conditions for active joint learning activities of students in different learning situations. Students are different - some quickly “grasp” all the teacher’s explanations, easily master lexical material and communication skills, others require not only much more time to comprehend the material, but also additional examples and explanations. Such guys, as a rule, are embarrassed to ask questions in front of the whole audience, and sometimes they simply do not realize that they specifically do not understand and cannot formulate the question correctly. If in such cases we combine students into small groups (3-4 people each) and give them one common task, stipulating the role of each student in the group in completing this task, then a situation arises in which everyone is responsible not only for the result of their work (which is often leaves him indifferent), but also, most importantly, for the results of the entire group. Therefore, weak students try to find out from the strong students all the questions they do not understand, and the strong ones are interested in ensuring that all members of the group, first of all, the weak students, thoroughly understand the material, and at the same time, the strong student has the opportunity to check his own understanding of the issue, to get to the very essence. In this way, through joint efforts, gaps are closed. This is the general idea of collaborative learning [3,86].

It should be noted that it is not enough to form groups and give them appropriate tasks. The point is that the student wants to acquire knowledge himself. Working together provides an excellent stimulus for cognitive activity and communication, since in this case you can always count on help from your comrades. The teacher can pay much more attention to individual students because everyone is busy.

This type of technology can be used when studying the topic “Nouns that have only a singular form”: students are given the task to divide into three groups and select words that have only a singular form: 1 group - names of groups of people; Group 2 - names of substances; Group 3 - names of qualities and actions. Each group should have a strong, average and weak student. Since the grade of the group will depend on the work of each student, all participants will try to complete the task correctly, and weak students will delve into the essence of the task and try to complete it, and “strong” students will help them in this. Thus, every student will be involved in completing this task.

Modular learning and its elements are also actively used in the practice of teaching the Russian language. Modular learning is based on an activity-based approach to learning: only that educational content is consciously and firmly assimilated by the student, which becomes the subject of his active actions. Modular learning is based on the theory of developmental learning, the foundations of which were laid by J.I. Vygotsky. The implementation of this learning theory requires that the learner be constantly in his zone of proximal development. In modular training, this is achieved by differentiating the content and dose of student assistance in organizing educational activities in different forms: individual, pair, group, and in rotating pairs [4,31].

The Russian language teaching material, which includes a complete block of information, a targeted programme of action and teacher's advice on its successful implementation, is highlighted as the basis. The teaching material is divided into thematic blocks, each thematic block fits within the strict time limits of a two-hour lesson. In order to better assimilate the content of the thematic block, the teacher follows the stages of the rigid structure of the modular lesson: repetition, perception of the new, comprehension, consolidation of what has been learnt, control. Each stage begins with a target setting and an indication of the system of actions; each stage of the lesson ends with a control to establish the success of learning. With the help of the modules, the teacher manages the learning process. In the training session itself, the teacher's role is to form positive motivation of the student, to organise, coordinate, advise, control.

One of the most interesting types of teaching technologies is a pedagogical workshop. The workshop, an unusual form of lesson delivery, was developed in the practice of French teachers, representatives of the New Education Group (P. Langevin, Henri Vallon, Jean Piaget, etc.) [5,259]. The essence of the technology under consideration is that in the atmosphere of a uniquely organised learning process the students themselves acquire and comprehend knowledge of the Russian language.

In the traditional organisation of the learning process, in general, and in particular in Russian language, the source of knowledge is always only the teacher. In the workshop, conditions are created for students to independently put forward an idea, the further development of which takes place both in individual, group and collective work. In the process of joint thinking about the problem, it is possible to transfer learning to a new qualitative level, which leads to a new vision of the problem.

The game form of classes is created with the help of game techniques and situations that act as a means of inducing and stimulating students to educational activities. Gaming technology has enormous potential. The game itself organizes training. But it's not easy to play seriously. At first, many problems may arise: how to play without disrupting the lesson? How to behave? How do you want to play? What to play? Any game will be many times more effective if played openly, that is, discuss with students why the game is being played, why the rules are as they are, whether the game can be complicated, changed, improved. Often such discussion brings more benefits than the game itself, developing the student's creativity and thinking and, in addition, laying the foundation for a gaming culture [6,112].

In this regard, we believe that the use of innovative and game technologies in Russian language lessons contributes to the development of students' cognitive activity and an increase in the quality of knowledge, since the inertia of the organization of training, as well as the weak development and dissemination of organizational innovations in the field of education - is now the main obstacle to the use of new technologies in the educational process. The development of such innovations and their active implementation, the implementation of policies in the field of the use of new technologies in education are the main way to improve the effectiveness of training at the moment.

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